

D8.1 – Serbia Arts & Sports as Resolution Media

“Running for their lives: Analysis of the use of arts and sports as media to challenge othering & forge intercultural dialogue and shared identities”

Serbia/Research Report D8.1

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About the Project

D.Rad is a comparative study of radicalisation and polarisation in Europe and beyond. It aims to identify the actors, networks, and wider social contexts driving radicalisation, particularly among young people in urban and peri-urban areas. D.Rad conceptualises this through the I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation) with the goal of moving towards measurable evaluations of de-radicalisation programmes. Our intention is to identify the building blocks of radicalisation, which include a sense of being victimised; a sense of being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures; and coming under the influence of “us vs them” identity formulations.

D.Rad benefits from an exceptional breadth of backgrounds. The project spans national contexts including the UK, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Finland, Slovenia, Bosnia, Serbia, Kosovo, Israel, Iraq, Jordan, Turkey, Georgia, Austria, and several minority nationalisms. It bridges academic disciplines ranging from political science and cultural studies to social psychology and artificial intelligence. Dissemination methods include D.Rad labs, D.Rad hubs, policy papers, academic workshops, visual outputs and digital galleries. As such, D.Rad establishes a rigorous foundation to test practical interventions geared to prevention, inclusion and de-radicalisation.

With the possibility of capturing the trajectories of seventeen nations and several minority nations, the project will provide a unique evidence base for the comparative analysis of law and policy as nation states adapt to new security challenges. The process of mapping these varieties and their link to national contexts will be crucial in uncovering strengths and weaknesses in existing interventions. Furthermore, D.Rad accounts for the problem that processes of radicalisation often occur in circumstances that escape the control and scrutiny of traditional national frameworks of justice. The participation of AI professionals in modelling, analysing and devising solutions to online radicalisation will be central to the project’s aims.

Executive Summary/Abstract

The purpose of this report is to explore the impact of deradicalization programs in Serbia and beyond throughout analysis of the self-evaluation and evaluation of the program participants. 'Boys' Day' (BD), a weekly program which was run by Info Park NGO in Belgrade, Serbia, is designed for unaccompanied refugee and asylum-seeking boys in the country, teenagers, and young adults. The report shall focus on the impact of BD, particularly in terms of relationship building, its fostering of peaceful co-existence between groups and its equipping of participants to manage difficulties faced in their lives as migrants and refugees. Hence, the paper aims to address the following questions: What impact does Boys Day have on relationship building between participants and within the local community? In what ways does Boys Day encourage and facilitate a peaceful co-existence of different communities, between whom may have previously existed conflict or hostility? To what extent do the topics covered, and skills learnt during Boys Day events allow participants to address challenges they face during life on the move? How the participants of the program comment of the I-GAP spectrum and what are the choices they are making?

Art & Sports as a means of alleviation social exclusion

1. Introduction

"We are enjoying when we are together": an exploration into the social impact of Info Park's 'Boys' Day' program for the asylum-seeking boys and young men

Serbia, especially Belgrade is the ethnographic benchmark. The purpose of this report is to offer a comprehensive result in the current changes in Europe and the historical conditions for Europe as a phenomenon of (de)radicalization become a part of the geographical reality i.e., migration processes. Therefore, this report is about refugees in Serbia and how Serbian-based NGOs work daily to help refugees in the realm of deradicalization capacities. Therefore, the ambition is to research their discourse on the issues connected to how Serbia is perceived as a receiving or transit country for refugees and other people on the move vulnerable to radicalization.

Moreover, the purpose of this report is to explore the impact of 'Boys' Day' (BD), a weekly program which was run by Info Park for unaccompanied refugee and asylum-seeking boys in Belgrade. The report shall focus on the impact of BD, particularly in terms of relationship building, its fostering of peaceful co-existence between groups and its equipping of participants to manage difficulties faced in their lives as outcasts and marginalized group. Hence, the paper aims to address the following research questions: What impact does Boys Day have on relationship building between participants and within the local community? In what ways does Boys Day encourage and facilitate a peaceful co-existence of different communities, between whom may have previously existed conflict or hostility? To what extent do the topics covered, and skills learnt during Boys Day events allow participants to address challenges they face during life on the move?

This report consists of two sections. The first one is the literature review, where we can see the insight from the research literature on arts, sports and social inclusions to capture the impact of arts /sports in developing resilience to anti-social behaviors/violence/extremism. The second section of the report is bringing arts /sports programmes in Serbia, performed by Info Park and their clients, that are specifically designed to challenge aspects of social isolation and discuss how these interventions can contribute to social interactions among members of socially disadvantaged groups.

As an average BD program combined both creative and sports activities, the following review of relevant research will explore both artistic and sports curricula in a variety of countries, in order to address the three research questions given in this introduction.

Methodology

In terms of the methodology of the report, the author performed desk research and literature review on policy framework in the field of (de)radicalisation and arts and sports programs. Primary sources, such as policy documents, were used at large depending on their public availability. The author also consulted research reports, scientific articles, newspaper articles, official websites, among other sources. Lastly, interviews with participants of the arts and sports activities dealing with radicalisation prevention and integration focusing on youth were presented.

According to several academic papers Serbia is perceived as a transition country for many refugees. Therefore, we would like to look further into this by adding the perspective of the NGO-workers who work with refugees every day. This aspect is in our research rarely seen in academic papers. One of the historical points of view is the refugee crisis the EU undertook in 2015 and will be put in perspective to the material we find in the field. This is particularly interesting because Serbia is a candidate country for the EU.

Research design for the present study comprised a combination of observation, individual interviews, and a pair interview. The author, as a long-term volunteer with Info Park, observed a BD session in November 2022. Following this, few interview sessions were conducted: one individual with a recent participant from Pakistan (Participant A), and one pair interview with two recent participants from Burundi (Participants B and C). All three of these participants attended BD until February 2023. The final interview was conducted with a previous participant from Afghanistan (Participant D), who went on to become a volunteer and then program facilitator and Info Park staff member. Due to Participant D's experience as both a participant and an organiser, this interview involved more in-depth questions about the ways in which his perception of BD changed during the progression of his role. Copies of the interview questions, adapted for the different participants, can be found in Figure 2 in the appendix. One interview was conducted in Serbian; hence both the original questions and their translations are included. This participant was also unable to answer three of the questions.

Due to scheduling difficulties and unforeseen circumstances, the author was only able to attend three BD sport event, and one art workshop. Moreover, author participated twice in an ordinary full-day program. Hence, the observation element of the study is limited to a general view of the atmosphere and behaviour of participants in their interactions with each other and facilitators. These observations shall be interwoven in the general discussion of findings from the interviews. Interview questions are visible in the appendix.

Intervention and focus groups. As part of the artwork activities, the final section of the workshop required participants to visualize their contemporary society, and their position in it. To allow participants to complete this task, Info Park provided them with paper and writing utensils (pencils, pens, or markers are sufficient). The direct question that followed the conversation was:

We would like to ask you to please draw how you imagine contemporary [Country where interview is held, Country of Origin and Desirable destination country] society. Please put where you see yourself. This way, each participant made three different drawings:

1. current one, from Serbia
2. one from the past (Country of Origin or previous residence) and,
3. future predictions (Country of Destination)

Prompt: Participants could draw it in any way or use any type of metaphor that they find meaningful

2. Literature review: Arts and Sports as a means of alleviating social exclusion

Multiple studies suggest that sports programs have value in addressing the notion of 'othering.' For the purposes of this paper, the author adopts the definition of 'othering' taken by Grove and Zwi (2006: 1933), namely that of a process which 'defines and secures one's own identity by distancing and stigmatising another'. An example of one such sports program that took steps to diminish othering and to promote inclusion is explored by Doidge et al. (2020), who researched the impact of a refugee integration program at a table tennis club in Brighton, UK. In this club, refugees, who themselves were from a variety of countries, participated alongside individuals from many other backgrounds. Other groups represented included people who were homeless, people with Down's Syndrome, and people with physical disabilities (Doidge et al., 2020: 311). The variety of persons integrated into the club meant that refugees were not 'essentialised', nor made to stand out as different from other players. In the words of the club director: 'here you are not a refugee...you are a member of the club. Everybody is equal' (ibid.).

Similarly, Johns et al. (2014) evaluated a sports program in which individuals from different ethnic backgrounds played in a football team together. The youth mentoring program 'More than a Game' was implemented amongst young Muslim men in Melbourne and was run by an Australian Rules Football league club. The program offered football training, workshops on topics such as conflict resolution and counterterrorism, and football tournaments for mixed Muslim-Jewish teams. Participants in the program consistently reported that playing together as a team created a 'level playing field' (Johns et al., 2014: 63), as it was necessary for all players, regardless of their background, to obey the same rules. Indeed, many participants stated that their attitude towards different cultural groups changed as a result of the program, particularly towards those with a Jewish background, indicating that working alongside Jewish players in a sporting context enabled participants to set aside or challenge previous perceptions towards cultural differences (ibid.). This change in mindset amongst participants suggests that such sports programs can, in their inclusion of different social groups, contribute to combatting the process of

othering. Additionally, the shared equality amongst participants when playing together in a team, bound together with a common aim and the same rules, facilitated social relationships between players from different cultures that could otherwise have been schismatic (Johns et al., 2014: 63, 64).

Indeed, sports programs not only allow for the breaking down of social barriers between groups, but they also create a space in which social relationships and new communities can be formed. Flesner et al. (2021) explored integration strategies in a sports program for migrant children and youths in Sweden and found that relationship building between leaders and participants, and amongst participants themselves, was the main tool for leaders in promoting inclusion (Flesner et al., 2021: 75). Sports leaders gave significant time and effort to facilitate and promote social relationships. For example, from the outset of the program, leaders referred to participants in familial terms, a practice which was consequently adopted by participants amongst themselves (Flesner et al., 2021: 76). Similarly, in the study discussed above, Doidge et al. (2020) concluded that integration is only possible through the intentional and continual cultivation of relationships. The authors argue that such relationships must extend from within the club to everyday life outside for integration to be proven successful (Doidge et al., 2020: 314). For example, the table tennis club on which the authors concentrated their research organised various other social activities, such as football matches, as well as trips away to watch other sporting tournaments. In the context of this club, made up of many different social groups, such socialising and travelling together allowed the refugee players to further develop their friendships with players from different communities (ibid).

The idea that integration into a sports or arts community can drive further integration into wider society is also explored in other studies on both sports and arts programs. Stura et al. (2019), in researching factors which helped or impeded the ability of sports clubs to integrate refugees into German society, found that club participation allowed refugees to better learn the German language and local dialect, as well as helping them to understand their host country's gender roles and eating habits, which differed to those of their home countries (Stura et al., 2019: 138). Similarly, Pienimaki (2019), in researching the ways in which participatory photography can encourage social inclusion of young migrants in Finland, found that such programs can both give participants the feeling of group belonging, and, through organised photography workshop excursions, enable them to enhance their familiarity with the local area. The authors concluded that this increased familiarity with their new surroundings in turn contributed to enhanced social inclusion (Pienimaki, 2019: 1195).

In addition to aiding with integration, research suggests that, through giving migrants and refugees a space for self-expression and reflection, arts programs can help them to process previous experiences of trauma and current feelings of stress in their host countries. Akthar and Lovell (2018), for example, interviewed art therapists who worked one-to-one with refugee children and found that art therapy sessions, especially those focussing on storytelling, allowed children to begin to express

themselves around topics which they could not verbalise and to share their traumatic experiences (Akthar and Lovell, 2018: 144). The interviewed art therapists believed that the opportunity for clients to consider and explore the life changes that take place along the refugee journey through the means of art also helped them to build a new identity (Akthar and Lovell, 2018: 146). For instance, one therapist referred to the case of one of her clients, a refugee boy who had come from a high socio-economic background. In becoming a refugee, the boy felt that he had lost his dignity and sense of self. Through art therapy sessions, however, he was empowered through his taking control of art materials and the process involved in producing artwork, which allowed him to rebuild his self-esteem (ibid.). Further, Feen-Calligan et al. (2020) researched the extent to which a 12-week art therapy integration program was able to reduce stress symptoms for Syrian refugee youth in the US. The results of the study suggest that certain activities, such as weaving, encouraged senses of comfort and group belonging amongst participants. Other activities, such as collage making, contributed to a feeling of calmness as participants selected and arranged images (Feen-Calligan et al., 2020: 14, 15). After considering the benefits of these activities, the researchers concluded that art therapy sessions appear to be beneficial in reducing trauma-related symptoms among migrant youth (Feen-Calligan et al., 2020: 14).

Skills developed through sports programs also appear to help migrants and refugees in their navigation and coping with emotions and challenges faced in their new lives. In fact, for participants in Stura's (2019) study, the structured nature of sports training itself enabled them to cope better with their uncertain life circumstances. For many of the participants in Johns et al.'s (2020) study, the discipline required of them in their obligation to regularly attend training, as well as the discipline expected during the matches themselves, helped participants to develop greater self-control and conflict management skills both 'on and off the pitch' (Johns et al. 2020: 65). In addition, the negative connotations associated with rule breaking encouraged participants to improve their controlling of violent impulses. Indeed, one participant described the development of such qualities as 'not [only] useful on the pitch but also outside in society' (ibid.), showing that the abilities fostered in and through sport can be applied in everyday life.

It has been observed that, whilst a relatively large amount of research has been conducted separately into the impact of sports programs for refugee and migrant youth and the benefits of art therapy, there is little exploration into programs which combine aspects relating to both areas. Further, most of the research has been concentrated on the West, most notably Scandinavian and majority native English-speaking countries. There is a notable gap in the exploration of similar programs in Eastern Europe and Balkan countries such as Serbia. Hence, the current paper aims to fill this gap in research by exploring aspects of a program that encourages both self-expression (similar to the aim of the art therapy programs discussed above), practical education (the workshop content) and sports activities in a Western Balkan country.

3. Challenging otherness through Arts and Sports

Serbia received the first large groups of refugees and other migrants from Middle Eastern and West and South Asian countries in 2015. Due to its strategic geographical position at “the crossroads”, Serbia has become a crucial transit country on the Western Balkan Route – an entrepot for migrants trying to reach Western Europe. Serbia is usually the last stop for migrants before entering the Schengen area and the EU. In the second half of 2015, the so-called ‘Balkan route’ became a very popular path to the ‘destination’ countries, especially Germany. “*Serbia’s role has mainly been that of transit country; nevertheless, the migration flows have placed a humanitarian and financial strain on its asylum system*” (Lilyanova, October 2016: 1). Compared to the routes across the Mediterranean Sea, it is relatively safe and easy to travel through the Balkans (REACH, 2016). However, the introduction of different barriers has led to the significant increase of the use of illegal means for migration, that is, the migrants turn to the services offered by networks of smugglers operating along the route if they cannot cross the border regularly or reach the desired country through the requisite legal process. The tightening of control at the borders has also prompted the use of more dangerous routes, to circumvent those barriers.

Since 2015 Info Park has been working with people on the move. Info Park have conducted numerous projects focus on real needs of the clients: General refugee and migrant (RM) population, Vulnerable ones/UASCs - unaccompanied and separated children in need for protection from violence and harm of any kind; Vulnerable ones/W – women traveling in families, with children or alone, in need of overall protection and especially from gender-based violence. Regardless of target groups, Info Park teams or field officers at the locations will conduct a necessary list of the activities related to needs assessment, protection monitoring interviews in relation to their travel experience focusing on violence experiences, various forms of first aid (referrals to medical, psychological...), information sharing, asylum counselling, free legal aid in process of registration and camp access – and in general a promotion of staying in Serbia or Western Balkans instead of further travel.

a. Boys Day

Boys Day (BD) ran every Sunday from 2017 to 2023. The program involved sports activities, as well as creative and educational workshops on topics such as relationships, stress management and dealing with money. These workshops followed the ‘Boys on the Move’ curriculum: a life skills education scheme for unaccompanied and separated adolescent boys created by UNICEF (2019) and UNFPA.

A normal BD would begin at 11AM at the Info Park Hub in Belgrade. Participants were welcomed by the program facilitators on arrival and invited to respond to a weekly ‘check-in’ poster, on which they could circle, write, or draw something depicting the emotion that best described how they were feeling that day. Breakfast would then be provided, which participants and facilitators shared together. Breakfast was followed

by a workshop as outlined above, which usually began with participants being asked to share their opinions on the day's topic with the rest of the group. The program facilitator would then introduce the other workshop activities, which would ordinarily last for around an hour. Example photographs of posters used in the workshops can again be found in Figure 1 in the appendix. After the workshop, the group would form teams to take part in sports activities (typically games of football). In the spring and summer months, these football games would take place on Ada Ciganlija – an island on the river Sava in Belgrade, adapted for recreational purposes. The group would then return to the Info Park Hub in the late afternoon to allow time for participants to travel home before the evening.

BD participants generally lived in either the Obrenovac or Krjinača refugee reception centres, or in one of the UASC homes in Belgrade. The boys originated from a variety of countries, most commonly Afghanistan, Syria, and Iran. An average BD would include 10-15 participants, but attendance reached up to 20 boys and young men on some occasions.

b. Field Case Study and Intervention

Boardgames

Date: 4 August 2023 | Place: Obrenovac Asylum Centre | 15 attendees

Description: In the first part of the workshop, from 11AM to 1PM participants discussed a high risk of gender-based violence and human trafficking with the emphasis on the risk of migration. The goal of this activity was educational, for the participants to be aware about human trafficking, and the development of communication skills, perception, interaction, and empathy, thus the resilience. Games for the development of empathy and perception, PPT presentation as well as various icebreakers to increase focus were used for the implementation of the activity. During the second part of the day, from 2-4PM, a sports activity was planned, however, due to the high temperatures and tropical heat, participants decided to stay indoors and play some boardgames.

Attendees, especially the younger ones, were very interactive at the workshop, very open in communication, developed a lively discussion, citing examples from their experience. In addition, they showed high acting skills, which was also very useful, interesting, and fun for them, and as they stated, it was important for them to get information about the possibility of signing in, considering that they stay for a short time and hesitate because of the language barrier.

At the end of the workshop, participants pointed out that this type of activity is very useful for them, considering that it helps them to better understand their situation, and thus make an informed decision for the future, and that they would certainly continue to attend the same and similar activities.

Acquaintances

Date: 11 August 2023 | Place: Obrenovac Asylum Centre | 14 attendees

Similar like the previous workshop it started at 11AM, the first part was dedicated to introduction of the participants and free speech and open communication. The participants very quickly spoke openly about their experiences on the road, their dilemmas, and doubts, mutually exchanged their impressions and emotions so that this part of the workshop served as mutual group support, which, on the other hand, served as an excellent introduction to the topic of the workshop. The workshop was carried out in a combination of an educational workshop and a creative workshop. In the educational part, people on the move and facilitators were talking about emotions in the context of different types of relationships that we have with different people during our lives and their impact on the quality of life. During the presentation, lively discussions developed on several occasions when attendees talked about their

emotions in the context of family and friendship relationships. The discussion was particularly prompted by the obvious cultural difference between the participants themselves, as well as their assumptions about the differences in the destination countries. Special attention was drawn to the concept of "acquaintance", which is not known in the cultures of the participants, and they asked very specific and creative questions about this type of interpersonal relations with the aim of raising awareness of the value of this type of usual relations as well as possible emotional investment in such acquaintances.

A creative workshop also took place where the participants combined two types of art techniques. By combining drawings with collage elements, the participants learned to create a new context from opposite resources and thus respond to the topic of emotions, which stimulated their understanding of relationships and emotions in them, as well as the development of perception and creativity.

Cricket

Date: 18 August | Place: Ada Lake | 11 participants of the workshop, more than 30 people participated in cricket tournament.

That Friday a cricket tournament was organized in the morning. Since it happened on Friday, after the cricket, the participants and their friend had a lunch break, followed by a religious ceremony.

At 2:30PM, everyone gathered in the classroom where the activities continued. The workshop was organized into work in pairs with the aim of developing listening skills and understanding what was said, translation, interpretation as well as understanding the concept of consent. Also, through the games, the participants had the task of concluding what is needed for joint work and how to overcome difficulties, especially in the language barrier.

During the workshop, an atmosphere was created in which beneficiaries openly shared their experiences and communication difficulties they faced during their journey in foreign countries, openly asked questions and discussed, especially on the topic of setting healthy boundaries. At the end of the workshop, the participants pointed out that this type of activity was very useful for them and expressed their desire to continue with the workshop work.

Modelling and sculpting

Date: 25 August 2023 | Place: Info Park Hub | Participants: 13 attendees

From 11AM to 1PM, a creative modelling and sculpting workshop was organized. The participants used modelling tools for the first time, and during the work they discussed the topics covered in the previous workshops. In the second part of the workshop, from 14:30 to 16:00 scheduled for sports activities, only 5 users wanted to play

volleyball while the rest wanted to continue working in the classroom and talking. During the conversation, the participants discussed and exchanged opinions related to the discussed topics, openly asked questions, all with the aim of better overcoming possible obstacles in further integration.

At the end of the workshop, all the beneficiaries stated that it is very important for them to have activities of this type, where different techniques are combined to have the opportunity to acquire new manual and creative skills and learn new information that can be useful for them to overcome cultural differences and better integration into society.

c. Results and findings in relation to the I-GAP spectrum

As it was stated in the beginning of the report, D.Rad is a comparative study of radicalisation and polarisation in Europe that conceptualises radicalisation drivers through the I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation) especially among youth, and young people. The intention of the project is to identify the building blocks of radicalisation, which include a sense of being victimised; a sense of being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures, and this was an integral intention of this report as well. Thus, these trends work in synergy, but fall under different parts of I-GAP (injustices, grievance, alienation, polarisation,) spectrum, as it was discussed in this report.

The following section offers deeper analysis of selected quotes, drawing on the context elaborated in the previous section. However, I-GAP coding is of limited applicability in many cases and at this moment firmly in the position of power and doesn't perceive injustice as such, although actions are resulting in the polarisation between the participants and the current society.

From the perspective of I-GAP coding, the main motivational factors here are perceived as injustice. With the I-Gap, D.Rad project places the feeling of exclusion at the heart of the radicalisation processes of individuals. Hence, it proposes the importance of bolstering shared spaces in deradicalization as such spaces offer social interaction opportunities to those who gather around a common interest.

Interview answers consistently suggest that friendships were the most important part of BD for participants. Participant D, for example, stressed how important it was for him to spend time with and play football with other boys of a similar age and in a similar position to him. Through BD, he made friends with boys who have since moved to a variety of countries, but many of whom he remains in contact with, around five years after his first time at BD. When asked if he would have been friends with these boys if they had not been to BD together (Q9), Participant D reported that he would not have met many of the other participants otherwise, as many of them lived in either Krjnača or Obrenovac reception centres, which suggests that BD played an important role as a safe, neutral meeting place for the boys. Further, he shared that, through playing football in a team with participants with different backgrounds, he and others learnt how to better respect other cultures. He explained that the opportunity to share one's own thoughts and experiences on a particular topic during the workshops enabled participants to 'learn about five cultures in one day', allowing friendships between the boys to deepen as their understanding of each other increased. Participant A similarly emphasized that BD participants were 'all friends together', regardless of whether they were from Afghanistan, Pakistan, Syria, Morocco, or any of the other countries represented. He concluded his answer to Question 4 (which was concerned with whether and why the participant was friends with others at BD) with the statement, 'we helped one another, whoever had a problem'. Again, Participants B and C shared that the weekly event helped them to make more friends outside of their immediate social

circles in the reception centre and at school. Participant B stated that his favourite part of the BD was sitting and eating together whilst, 'talking about life' as it 'feel[s] great when we are together', a statement which appears to summarise the overall feeling of BD participants when they attend BD.

Additionally, during the observation, the author noticed a notably relaxed atmosphere at the Info Park hub throughout the day's program, and at the local bowling alley which we visited to play billiards. Participants seemed to enjoy the competitive but social element of playing the sport and it was clear, through the laughter and jokes shared between participants and program facilitators that, overall, participants felt comfortable with each other and with those leading them. Indeed, in reviewing the answers given by Participant D, it became clear to the author that, as a participant, he had developed both a great respect and a close friendship with the previous BD program facilitator, who is a native Serbian. When becoming a facilitator himself, Participant D said that he saw friendships being established between participants and leaders as one of the goals of the BD program: a priority that was mirrored in Flesner et al.'s (2021: 75) study, in which leaders from the outset created an inclusive and familial atmosphere. Indeed, in the present study, the author noticed that the program facilitators made effort to know and ask questions about the lives of the participants, showing their genuine care and interest for each individual.

The sport and recreational aspect of BD appears to have enabled a peaceful co-existence between local Serbian youth and BD participants, despite this not being a primary aim of the program. Participant D claimed that, during the regular trips to Ada for football games, it was common for other Serbian children and teenagers to join in the football games. This merging of the two groups was not an explicitly planned integration project, but rather happened coincidentally and organically as the groups became accustomed to meeting each other every Sunday afternoon. Indeed, Participant D noted that this experience 'helped kids realize that not all migrants are the same', a statement which implies he believed that local youth perhaps held preconceptions towards refugees. Similarly, participants in Waardenburg et al.'s (2018) study stated that they took part in sports activities outside of reception centres in order to shed the 'refugee' label, as they felt that the term itself evoked negative characteristics. In the present study, Participant D went on to describe how keen the local Serbian young people were to keep playing with the BD participants each week, which led to friendships being formed between members of the two groups. According to Bjekić et al.'s (2020) research report into attitudes towards migrants and refugees in Serbia, less than 20% of Serbian citizens had any form of contact with migrants and refugees, yet 40% harbored negative emotions towards those arriving from Africa and the Middle East. An application of these statistics suggests it is likely that the majority of Serbian youth who joined the BD football games did not have any prior contact with refugees, but the presence of BD activities in a popular public recreational space allowed this positive first contact to be made. This contact in turn contributed to a diminishing of 'othering' (Grove and Zwi, 2006: 1933) between the two groups. Hence,

the impact of BD substantiates the conclusion made by Johns et al. (2014: 68), that sport holds a vital role in facilitating social interaction and friendships between different groups who held preconceptions towards the other due to not previously having had contact with each other.

Similarly to the findings of Stura (2019: 138), which indicated that sports clubs activities helped migrant participants understand different gender roles and laws, BD allowed participants to learn about local customs. For example, Participant D explained that, when boys first started coming to BD, it was common for them to be unwilling to sit next to women or girls on the bus journey to Ada. Through conversations with the program facilitators and discussions during the workshops, participants learnt that this was acceptable and expected in Serbian culture. Additionally, Participant D claimed that participants also learnt about respectful Serbian etiquette, such as giving up your seat on the bus for a pregnant woman or the elderly. It appears that simple shared experiences such as travelling on a bus together with program facilitators allowed participants to learn inductively the societal expectations in their new country, and hence adapt to a new way of life. Additionally, the journey itself between the Info Park Hub and Ada, which takes approximately thirty minutes on public transport, will have allowed participants to enhance their geographical knowledge of the local area, similarly to those in Pienimaki's (2019: 1195) study.

Participant D emphasized the value of learning how to express yourself eloquently and how to behave in a group – two skills he believed participants developed through the opinion-sharing exercise at the start of each workshop session. As outlined above, each participant would be asked to stand up in front of the group and share his thoughts on the session's topic as an introductory exercise. Participant D said he felt that practicing this every week helped participants to 'lose that shy part' of their character that could emerge in a group setting. Further, similarly to the refugee clients of art therapists in Atkhar and Lovell's (2018: 145) study, who benefited from the support and mutual understanding of other art therapy participants when working in a group, this opinion-sharing exercise in BD also enabled participants to grow more and more comfortable with one another.

All four participants expressed that BD allowed them to improve their football skills and become better players. Indeed, participants A and D said that the opportunity to play football with others in a team was their primary reason for attending BD in the beginning. Whilst developing better sports skills may not directly appear to help participants to address challenges they face in their lives, participant responses in Waardenburg et al.'s (2018) and Stura's (2019: 134) studies suggest that for refugees (in these cases, particularly those living in reception centres) sport provides a form of relief and relaxation, helping them to cope better with the stressful and uncertain nature of their lives. In addition, on becoming a BD facilitator, Participant D expressed the importance of BD in creating a space which allowed children to be children, giving

them the opportunity to take part in activities which resemble a childhood: something that is easily lost for young people on the move (Concern Worldwide US, 2020). Participant D emphasized the role of the leaders in 'keep[ing] them happy for one day', in which they appear to have succeeded; for example, one of the younger participants from Afghanistan would contact Participant D regularly throughout the week, asking when it was Sunday as he was so much looking forward to the following BD.

Some participants spoke about specific aspects of the workshops which they found particularly beneficial. For example, Participant D said he found the workshop focusing on money-saving very useful for his everyday life. Additionally, Participants B and C shared that they learnt important IT skills through attending BD. For instance, through BD, the participants were able to set up their own Gmail account and learn how to use it effectively, along with other functions of Google that they had never used before.

Participants B and C spoke about how participation in BD enabled them to learn how to 'live with people', and, although they did not expand further upon this point, this skill is no doubt vital when living amongst high numbers of people from a variety of cultures in a reception centre setting. This claim is corroborated by Waardenburg et al. (2018), who state that the nature of reception centres in accommodating people from a wide selection of cultures results in 'internal differences' and hence a 'lack of togetherness'. Indeed, events such as BD hence hold great importance in allowing individuals from different cultures (indeed, three countries are represented in just the four participants in this study) to learn how to co-exist and, further, to develop friendships as described above.

Paradox of vulnerability in relation to the I-GAP

During the interviews and analysis, author discern the creation of the so-called paradox of 'vulnerable groups,' whereby people considered the most vulnerable tend to have better access to services en route and in destination contexts, while people not considered vulnerable are rendered more vulnerable due to lack of access. It is the perceived vulnerability of an unaccompanied child or a woman travelling alone that ensures better protection and increased resilience in transit and destination countries in Europe.

Conclusion

This report reflected on the importance of communal support, where and when vulnerable people have a chance to spend time together in spaces mainly reserved for them and their needs. This way, these people make the (in)formative decisions which helps them to think differently, and to find the best possible ways of thinking about themselves, despite all the obstacles coming from their various identities. Therefore, the report suggests that arts and as a resolution media may be successfully used in deradicalization processes. In terms the Boys Day program clearly had a positive impact on relationship building between unaccompanied boys on the move. Not only does the program create a space in which boys in similar positions are able to meet for the first time, it also gives them the opportunity to get used to playing with one another in a team, as well as eating and participating in the workshops together. Indeed, each participant expressed that the friendships established through Boys Day were the highlight of the program: a feeling summarized by Participant B, who said, 'we do all things together' and 'we are enjoying when we are together'.

These friendships also extended beyond the Sunday meetings – indeed, Participant D spoke about his ongoing friendships with people he first met through the program, who have since moved all over Europe. Although, friendships between participants seemed to be the primary impact of BD in terms of relationship building, the intentional efforts made by program facilitators to get to know individual participants, as well as the opportunity the football games at Ada presented for participants to mix with local boys, evidently also had a positive impact in terms of relationship building and establishing connections within the local community.

Indeed, the interactions between participants and local teenagers, facilitated through games of football, cricket and other sport activities in encouraging a peaceful co-existence between communities who may have held negative preconceptions towards each other. According to Bjekić et al. (2020) it is unlikely that the Serbian youth present at Ada would have otherwise met young refugees, hence Boys Day was able to act as a bridge between the two groups, as well as to enable friendships to be formed. A peaceful co-existence of different communities, between whom may have previously existed conflict or hostility wasn't shown or confirmed. However, as none of the participants explicitly referred to unlikely friendships amongst themselves (i.e., between individuals with whom relationships would otherwise have been conflict-ridden had they not met through BD), this aspect of the research question remains to be further explored through additional research.

To address skills learnt during workshops and related events, participants allowed to address challenges they face during life on the move, it appears that the topics covered, and skills learnt through the BD program did allow participants to address challenges they faced in their day-to-day lives, as some sort of survival. Participants generally seemed to struggle to remember specific topics addressed in the workshops,

hence their responses were rather vague. However, this is likely because BD has not been able to run since December. Despite this, there was a generally positive response regarding the usefulness of the workshops. Sessions covering technological skills and money-saving were specifically mentioned as being helpful by participants B, C and D, and Participant D recalled that the workshop on stress was particularly beneficial in allowing the boys to understand the different perspectives of participants according to their cultures. Additionally, BD enabled participants to improve their football skills; as this was something that all four participants greatly enjoyed; this sporting element enabled them to relax whilst also learning how to work alongside each other in a team environment.

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Appendix 2: Sports in action.

Appendix 3: Workshop, focus groups participants.

Appendix 4: Best Practices/Interventions/Programmes

Title	Institution(s), Place	Aims	Source	PLACE
<p><i>Virtual Becomes Reality</i></p> <p>*this initiative is part of CoE's campaign <i>No Hate Speech Movement</i></p>	CSO Libero	Prevention of digital violence; educational programmes focused on children and youth	link	Online
<p>Trening <i>Zaustavimo govor mržnje</i> (Training <i>Let's stop hate speech</i>)</p> <p>*this action is part of Serbian National Campaign against Hate Speech</p>	Krovna organizacija mladih Srbije i Institut za medije i različitosti Zapadni Balkan	Raising youth's awareness of hate speech consequences; offering broader understanding of freedom of expression and hate speech; training for peer educators	link	Online
<p><i>Anonimna mržnja</i> (Anonymous Hatred)</p>	CSOs Belgrade Centre for Human Rights and LIBER New Media Centre	Raising public awareness about online hate speech and suggesting the mechanisms for countering hate speech, particularly the responsibility and punishment policy	link	Belgrade
<p>Sandžak: POLITIKE IDENTITETA I PREVENCIJA EKSTREMIZMA,</p>	Helsinki Committee for Human Rights	Theatre play	link	Novi Pazar

mart 2020. (helsinki.org.rs)				
Resilience: Civil Society for Media Free of Hate and Disinformation	SEENPM	Six tv shows that reflects research results	Link	
Youth Leadership Programme	PIN	express oneself through a song, a video or online content	Link	Online
Pozorišna predstava „Kako ja ovo sinu da objasnim?“	Centar E8	The play talks about extremism, how it occurs and what are its consequences. From ethnic, religious to the very radical non-acceptance of those different from oneself, extremism is becoming a big problem in today's society.	Link	Belgrade, theatre play travelled through Serbia
Svi u glas!	Choir Svi u Glas	A choir started for ethnic Roma children at risk of poverty has grown into a musical-educational platform that connects all those interested in singing, listening – and understanding each other.	Link	Perform all around Serbia
Café Bar Sixteen	Kafe bar 16	Cafe Bar 16 in Cetinjska Street in Belgrade is, just at first glance, a cafe like any other. Apart from good coffee	Link	Belgrade

		and the smiles of the employees, it offers much more than that – work and security for young people from Svratishte, who mostly live in extreme poverty.		
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